

BUILT 06

Mobility at home

How to help older adults to move safely about their home and to reduce risk of falls.

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Warsaw University
of Technology

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BUILT

MODULE 6

Mobility at home

In this module you will learn how to help older adults to move safely about their home and to reduce risk of falls.

Mobility

Optimal mobility is defined as being able to safely and reliably go:

- where you want to go,
- when you want to go,
- in a way you want to get there.

Optimal mobility is one of the key components of healthy ageing.

Mobility is a broad issue which refers to movement in all of its forms. Basic ambulation, moving from a bed to a chair, walking for leisure and the completion of daily tasks, driving a car are various forms of mobility.

This module will help you to identify the key aspects of safe movement of older adults at home, the risk of falls at home and identify possible strategies to reduce falls risk as well as good practices in fall detection.

What will you learn

- 1 Techniques for safe movement around home in old age
- 2 What are the main causes and consequences of falls in old age
- 3 Strategies to reduce risk of fall at home
- 4 What are the good practices in fall detection

Chapters in this module

1 Safe movement

2 Falls

3 Reduce risk

4 Falls detection

BUILT

MODULE 6

CHAPTER 1

Safe movement

This chapter will provide information about strategies for moving safely in the home.

What will you learn in this chapter

- 1 Techniques for moving safely around the home
- 2 Types of products that may be helpful for issues to do with mobility indoors

Safe movement – slow movement

Moving and walking in old age is more demanding than at younger ages. Physical and physiological characteristics such as muscle strength and endurance decrease with age. Older adults in general have declining ability and desire to walk. Safe movement strategies are essential for staying active. It is crucial to move despite barriers, even chronic pain. Continuing to walk will improve strength, balance, flexibility, and endurance. The easiest solution in mobility problems is to move slower, particularly when getting up from the chair or the bed. Fast movements can lead to sudden blood pressure drop, dizziness and fainting.

Choose the right seats

By choosing the right seats, you can help an older adult who has movement problems. This takes into consideration: height, firmness, armrests and chair size.

- Make sure that the height of a seat ensures easy getting up. In general higher seats are easier to use. Avoid seats that are low.
- Firmness of seat is important because it is easier to get up from a firm chair than from a soft one.
- Chairs with arms may be much easier to get out of, as the arms can be used as leverage. Remember to check if the arms are sturdy enough.
- The right size of the chair is also significant especially for people with excessive weight.

Use mobility aids

Encourage older adults to use mobility aids when they need them: canes, walkers and rollators, different types of braces: back, knee, shoulder or hip braces, crutches. Remember that older adults may feel embarrassed to use them. Sometimes it maybe difficult to encourage them. You can persuade older adults by explaining the increased independence that comes with use of an aid. Ask professionals for opinion and advice. A professional's suggestion to use mobility aids may be more persuasive. There are many options. Let the person who will be the primary user of the aid choose the make and model.

Use assisting tools

Our homes should support our mobility. Adequate equipment is of vital importance. A good example of this is handrails installed on walls. The modern design of this handrail is not stigmatizing and indicating someone's restrictions. They are not very expensive and can be installed in many places. An important thing to consider is the construction of the wall which should have the capacity to hold the rail and the user.

Use assisting tools

With the occurrence of some mobility restrictions older adults should not adapt themselves to the equipment but contrary the equipment should support them in remaining longer independent and healthy. A good example of such a solution is this example of lowering upper cabinets which enables a wheelchair user to pick things that would otherwise be unreachable.

Use lifting aids

Lifting aids are for instance portable electric lifting seats or full lift chairs. They are very helpful for people who experience difficulties with standing-up. An older person sitting on such a chair can stand up by themselves which positively influences their self-esteem and subsequently their mental health.

Standing up from a chair

One of the most common problems for older adults, especially those who have back pain, is how to stand up from a chair. This video presents a proper technique for standing up.

Watch the video:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nJEP2CE8oGM>

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 BUILT | **MODULE 6** | **CHAPTER 1**

Arrange steps of getting up in the correct order

1. Push up with your legs
2. Bring your strong leg back
3. Slide to the edge of the chair
4. Spread out of your feet
5. Lean forward until you feel your bottom coming off the chair

Standing up from a chair with a walker

A walker-rollator is a very helpful mobility aid. However, standing up with a walker may be challenging. The video presents a proper technique for standing up from a chair with a walker.

Watch the video:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=D3gsPxbe9RA>

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 BUILT | **MODULE 6** | **CHAPTER 1** Safe movement

Arrange steps of getting up with a walker in the correct order

1. Put one hand on the chair
2. Push up
3. Transfer hand from chair to the walker
4. Slide to the edge of the chair
5. Put one hand on the walker
6. Bring your strong leg back

Suggestions for further watching

[How to walk with a cane correctly](#)

[How to use crutches correctly](#)

[How to use walker correctly](#)

[How to open doors with cane, crutches and walker](#)

[How to use walker on stairs](#)

[How to use crutches on stairs](#)

[How to use cane on stairs](#)

At the table

Mobility at the table is also quite an important issue. The table should allow the user to sit comfortably and provide enough space for the dishes. The chairs should be cosy but at the same time easy to clean and move.

We should also pay attention to the right table setting. Special plates and cups, as well as cutlery, dedicated to older adults supporting them in eating by themselves are available on the market. The ability to eat by oneself is vital as it largely influences self-esteem.

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 BUILT **MODULE 6** **CHAPTER 1** Safe movement

Optimal mobility is one of the key components of healthy ageing.

True

False

Chapter summary

1

You have learned about safe movement principles for older adults.

2

This knowledge will help you to understand what techniques should be applied when moving around the home and what additional advice may be used to help older adults.

3

You may help other facilitators to assist older adults in simple indoor mobility issues.

4

The next chapter – Falls is recommended as a continuation of this course

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

1

You know techniques about moving safely in the home

2

You know what additional advice may be helpful for indoor mobility issues

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

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BUILT

MODULE 6

CHAPTER 2

Falls

In this chapter you will find information about risk factors, consequences and cost of falls.

Falls

The most common injury among people over 60 is as a result of falls. Falls present a significant threat to health and well-being among older people and are a major cause and contributor to morbidity, disability and premature death.

Maintaining an upright body position requires constant cooperation of the sense of eyesight with the brain and muscles. With ageing, the risk of falls increases as ability to control balance reduces. In this chapter you will learn to identify the most important causes and consequences of falls in old age.

What will you learn in this chapter

- 1 What are the main risk factors of falls
- 2 What are the main consequences of falls
- 3 How high are the costs of falls

Did you know?

From 20 to 60 % of falls are at home, during minor house duties such as replacing bulbs, washing windows or hanging curtains.

Source:

<https://zdrowie.pap.pl/sites/default/files/dokumenty/materialy-edukacyjne-dla-wykladowcow.pdf>

Causes of falls

Falls occur as the result of many risk factors. According to WHO those are categorized into four dimensions:

- biological risk factors,
- behavioural risk factors,
- environmental risk factors,
- socioeconomic risk factors.

Biological risk factors

Biological risk factors are related to age, gender and race. This group of factors covers also chronic diseases such as Parkinson's, Arthritis or Osteoporosis as well as general physical, physiological and cognitive decline of older adults.

The interaction of biological factors with behavioural and environmental ones increases the risk of falling. For example vision impairment leads to a higher level of fragility which intensifies the risk of falling due to environmental hazards.

Behavioural risk factors

This group of factors include those which are related to daily choices, human actions and emotions. There is a possibility to quite easily modify them through behavioural change unlike biological ones.

Strategies such as more physical activities, more social activities and healthy diet are very important in maintaining a good level of mobility in the old age.

 Did you know?

According to WHO approximately 28-35 % of people aged of 65 and over fall each year increasing to 32-42 % for those over 70 years of age.

Environmental risk factors

Environmental risk factors are not a direct cause of falls rather the interaction between other groups of factors such as biological or behavioural ones. The existence of biological or behavioural factors increases exposure to environmental ones. In this group we have home hazards such as narrow steps, slippery surfaces, stairs, looser rugs, low lighting, wires on the floor, sockets located very low and many more. Despite the fact that there are many such hazards, sometimes simple and cheap strategies help to deal with them – if you want to find more please see the next chapter – Reduce risk.

Socioeconomic risk factors

Economic status, social conditions and the ability of the community to face the previously mentioned conditions are one of the main socioeconomic related issues. Socioeconomic risk factors include: low income, low education, low IT literacy, limited access to health services and social care, lack of community resources, poor and inadequate housing conditions. Such factors have a strong influence on other factors for example low income can lead to malnutrition or obesity as a result of unhealthy and inadequate diet.

Do the task!

Nikos is vulnerable to falls due to different factors. Identify them.

- ✓ Meet and get to know Nikos. [You can find information about Nikos here.](#)
- ✓ Read leaflet about Nikos and find information about possible risk factors for Nikos.
- ✓ Use different groups of factors described in the chapter to order Nikos risk factors.
- ✓ Check the answers and compare.

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 BUILT | **MODULE 6** | **CHAPTER 2** Falls

Which risk factors from presented groups does Nikos have to deal with?

Behavioural risk factors	Nikos has non-routine work, which makes it difficult for him to follow his medication and lifestyle intervention (exercise, food) properly. Nikos is also an occasional smoker and is having too many different medications.
Socioeconomic risk factors	Nikos cannot afford to pay for professional support with managing a daily healthy lifestyle and with having too many different medications. Nikos job was affected by a financial crisis in Greece, and he now has to work more hours to make up for it.
Biological	Diabetes, high cholesterol and high blood pressure

Consequences of falls

Falls can result in a variety of complications ranging from soft injuries to long-term hospitalisation and serious psychological and social consequences. The main groups of consequences are:

- physical,
- social,
- psychological.

Physical consequences

Some key physical consequences of falls include pain and discomfort, fractures, especially at the hip or forearm. Difficulty or inability to move around independently may occur as a result of fall, sometimes for long periods of time. Prolonged immobility can lead to serious consequences such as unsteady walking pattern and medical conditions or health problems. Head and brain injuries may be severe consequences of falls as well.

Social consequences

Major social consequences of falls are related to the less participation in society. As a result of falls, older adults may lose independence and have to change their daily routine. Long-term hospitalisation or home isolation after a fall may lead to a loss of social contacts. Social consequences also includes financial costs related to hospitalisation. All previously mentioned consequences lead to decreased quality of life and wellbeing.

Psychological consequences

Loss of independence, especially in daily routines, causes frustration and fear of falling again. Older adults may feel distress due to uncertainty and experience chronic anxiety after suffering from a fall-related injury. Some older adults are too embarrassed to use walking aids such as a cane. This leads to loss of self-esteem due to an inability to take care of oneself after falling. Some older adults suffer from post-fall syndrome (PFS) which results from a combination of neurological and motor symptoms and psychological disorders. It appears either insidiously due to an increase of frailty or suddenly after a trauma (fall) or an operation. The worst case scenario is when an older adult dies due to PFS.

 Did you know?

According to different studies more than 40 % of older adults may experience post-fall syndrome (PFS) following a fall.

Source:

<https://www.karger.com/Article/Abstract/511356>

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877065717302257>

Costs of falls

Falls result in significant costs. The economic costs of falls are critical not only to the family or carers but also to community and society in terms of healthcare and social service utilisation. The cost of hospitalisation after falls is increasing significantly all over the world. It can be estimated that at least 25 billion € are spent treating fall-related injuries across the EU every year. Shifting demographics over the next 35 years could result in annual fall-related expenditures exceeding 45 billion euros by the year 2050. Among different healthcare cost items, the cost of hospital inpatient services is the greatest and the second highest is the long-term care.

Additionally, there are also indirect costs such as loss of productivity of family caregivers and sometimes inability to work while caring. Even if family caregivers are culturally and morally accepted, falls put a huge burden on the household budget.

If you want to find more information:

<https://extranet.who.int/agefriendlyworld/wp-content/uploads/2014/06/WHO-Global-report-on-falls-prevention-in-older-age.pdf>

[https://eupha.org/repository/sections/ipsp/Factsheet falls in older adults in EU.pdf](https://eupha.org/repository/sections/ipsp/Factsheet_falls_in_older_adults_in_EU.pdf)

Did you know?

The mean costs per fall in The Netherlands between 2007 and 2009 were €9370 and increased with age (from €3900 at ages 65–69 years to €14,600 at ages ≥ 85 year).

Source:

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0020138312001301>

Did you know?

There is a European initiative called Prevention of Falls Network Europe (ProFaNE) which promotes good practice in taxonomy and clinical trial methodology as well as detailed clinical assessment and management protocols for those 'at risk' of falls.

<http://www.profane.eu.org/>

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 BUILT | **MODULE 6** | **CHAPTER 2** Falls

The most common injury among people over 60 is as a result of fall.

- True
- False

Chapter summary

1

You have learned about the main risk factors and consequences of falls in old age.

2

This knowledge will help you to understand why mobility of older adults is a key issue for their wellbeing.

3

You may help other facilitators to understand why mobility of older adults is so important not only for them but also for the whole society, and which factors have influence on this.

4

This course should have strong influence on perception of mobility of older adults as a key issue for their wellbeing and general health.

5

The next chapter – Reduce risk is recommended as a continuation of this course and all HEALTHY modules.

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

1

You know about the main causes and consequences of falls

2

You know the cost of falls

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

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BUILT

MODULE 6

CHAPTER 3

Reduce risk

In this chapter you will find information about architectural solutions and strategies which reduce risk of falls.

Reduce risk of falls

Older adults can be protected from falls by changes in behaviour and changes in the environment. At first, it is about changing lifestyle into a healthy one. Prevention is the key to healthy ageing and avoiding falls. There is also huge range of modifications that could be introduced in the surroundings (living environment) to increase comfort and safety of older adults. These include age-friendly architectural solutions and even simple strategies which significantly reduce the risk of falls. In this chapter such strategies are presented.

What will you learn in this chapter

- 1 What are the age-friendly architectural solutions that help reduce the risk of falls
- 2 What are strategies in reducing risk of falls

Strategies to reduce risk of falls at home

1**2****3**

Remove rugs, carpets and doorsteps

Older adults tend to not lift their feet as they walk as each step brings the risk of a fall due to loose or slippery rugs. One strategy to deal with this is to remove rugs and carpets from the floor, especially those which are floppy with fringes or creases. Removing doorsteps is important as well. If an individual do not want to get rid of their rugs, he or she can secure loose rugs with double-sided tape, tacks or a slip-resistant backing.

Strategies to reduce risk of falls at home

1

2

3

Proper lighting

Older adults cannot always see so well in a dark or shadowed room. Better, brighter lighting can help to light the way. On this same subject, it is useful to assess the location of light switches. These may be out of reach for wheelchair users. Place night lights in bedrooms, bathrooms and hallways. Make clear paths to light switches that aren't near doorways. Consider trading traditional switches for glow-in-the-dark or illuminated switches. Try to supplement home lighting with additional lamps especially in places where older adult spend most of their time.

Strategies to reduce risk of falls at home

1

2

3

Get rid of unnecessary things

Remove unnecessary items from the floor to make more space and to ease access to important items such as the telephone. Move coffee tables, magazine racks and plant stands from high-traffic areas. If it is possible get rid of redundant items or furniture because it is easier to move when there is more space.

Strategies to reduce risk of falls at home

4

5

6

Hide wires

Wires on the floor dramatically increase the risk of falls. Hide them behind the furniture.

Strategies to reduce risk of falls at home

4

5

6

Use slippers

Slippers should be on an older adult's feet not under the bed or in the wardrobe. The risk of a fall without slippers is higher. The use the right footwear should be treated as a part of a fall-prevention plan. Instead of high heels or floppy slippers, properly fitting, sturdy shoes with non-skid soles should be worn.

Strategies to reduce risk of falls at home

4

5

6

Make it nonslip

Non-slip mats are necessary in a bathroom. They may be helpful in the hall or in the kitchen as well. If there is a place with slippery floors use non-slip mats. Try to keep surfaces clean and dry.

Strategies to reduce risk of falls at home

7

8

9

Use mobility aid

If an older adult has serious walking problems propose using a mobility aid. It reduces the risk of falls significantly. This could be a walker, a cane, or a motorized scooter. As with any mobility aid, it should be properly fitted for the best and easiest use.

Older adults may find that using a walker or other mobility aids increases their freedom, independence, and quality of life.

Strategies to reduce risk of falls at home

7

8

9

Move more

Regular activity keeps the body stronger which reduces risk of falls. Older adults should take part in regular physical activities. Whether through regular walking or light exercising and stretching, an active older adult can remain more stable than a sedentary person. A training program to prevent falls should include the following: strength training, balance training and endurance training. If you want to know more about physical activity see the HEALTHY modules.

Strategies to reduce risk of falls at home

7

8

9

Eat healthy

Healthy diet just like regular physical activities, is one of the key issues in prevention of falls. You can find more about healthy diet in HEALTHY Modules.

Strategies to reduce risk of falls at home

If health related problems occur go to the doctor
If an older adult has problems such as balance disorders or recurrent dizziness they should go to the doctor as soon as possible.

Strategies to reduce risk of falls at home

Keep it clean

Untidiness in the home is the cause of many falls because it is easy to overlook loose wires, rolled carpets or slippery surfaces in an unclean home . Keeping the home clean is a very important strategy to avoid the risk of a fall.

Reduce risk strategies checklist

1

Remove rugs, carpets and doorsteps

2

Proper lighting

3

Get rid of unnecessary things

4

Hide wires

5

Use slippers and non-slip mats

6

Use mobility aid

7

Move more

8

Eat healthy

9

If health related problems occur go to the doctor

10

Keep it tidy

Did you know?

Adapting older adult's apartment according to their changing needs is one of the best strategies in reducing risk of falls, however it can be costly as well. Interventions such as installing handrails, balustrades or special brackets on stairs, as well as in bathrooms and other vulnerable places are examples of common adaptations. More information about the need of adaptation is included in BUILT Module 1. Possible apartment adaptations are presented in BUILT Modules 2 and 3.

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 BUILT **MODULE 6** **CHAPTER 3** Reduce risk

Prevention is the key to healthy ageing and avoiding falls.

True

False

Chapter summary

1

You have learned about strategies to reduce the risks of falls in older age.

2

This knowledge will help you to understand how simple behavioural changes and changes of environment can make a huge difference for the mobility of older adults.

3

You may help other facilitators to eliminate existing risk of falls in older adults' apartments implementing simple and cheap strategies.

4

The next chapter – Fall detection is recommended as a continuation of this course and BUILT Modules 1, 2, 3 as well as all HEALTHY modules and SMART modules.

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

1

You know strategies and solutions in reducing risk of falls at home

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

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BUILT

MODULE 6

CHAPTER 4

Falls detection

This chapter provides information about fall detection devices. What are the available solutions and what should be taken into consideration before purchasing?

Falls detection

Even if older adults follow the strategies to reduce risk of falls, it is quite common that the older the person, the greater the risk. With the ever-growing ageing population, there is an urgent need for the development of fall detection systems. However, modern tele-monitoring technology can help. Many different types of personal alarm systems have already been developed, which in the event of a fall allow prompt calls for help (e.g., an ambulance, a loved one or a caregiver). It can even happen automatically, without the participation of the injured person. In this chapter you will find good practice examples of such technologies.

What will you learn in this chapter

- 1 What are the different types of fall detection devices
- 2 You will get to know good practice examples of fall detection devices
- 3 What are important factors that should be taken into consideration before the purchase of fall detection device

Fall detection devices

There is huge range of medical alert systems. The built-in technology can be worn depending on the device around the neck, on wrist or on waist. One prominent example is the currently popular smartwatches or bracelets which allow the wearer to monitor a range of medical factors discretely, and some of them detect a fall as well. Recently, the digital health world has stepped up its effort to create an alternative that's not only stigma-free but also proactive, detecting and even preventing falls. They may be received as fashionable and even desirable.

Fall detection devices detect and enable fast assistance for an older adult who is prone to falls.

An automatic detection medical alert system allows the user to summon help without having to press the call button – it activates the sensor if the user suffers a fall. However, some systems do not have an automatic alert.

Fall detection devices can evaluate body position, physical activity or pattern of movements. If abrupt changes of body movement occur and the device determines that these variables are within the danger zone, it will activate an emergency fall alert and call emergency response agents for assistance.

If you want to know more about types of fall detection devices go to SMART.

PacSana: A smart wristband

The PacSana bracelet with connection with two or more gateways is collecting data about the movement of older adults at home. It is supported by data analytics – The PacSana App and Desktop Dashboard which built the picture of the movement patterns of older person at home. If some anomalies occur and urgent assistance from carers is needed it allows the user to call for help easily. The bracelet and supportive app may also encourage older adults to set daily mobility goals that are important in prevention of falls. Moreover, the design of bracelet is similar to sport watches. You can find more information about the PacSana in the [European compendium of good practices on SHAFE](#) and on PacSana's [website](#).

Cloud based infographic of daily activity from PacSana,
Source: <https://pacsana.com/>

SiDLY

SiDLY band with Android application, Source: <https://sidly.eu/>

SiDLY is a telemedicine wristband, mobile application and 24-hour telecare platform. Telemedicine wristband monitors older adult's health 24/7 and detects dangerous situations for older adult's health and life for example falls. Among others it has an SOS button marked with Braille, a fall detector, wristband removal sensor or reminder to take medicine. In case of danger, it sends automatic information to the carer or rescuer. The wristband allows the user to make voice calls to a carer or rescuer and has modern design. You can find more information in the [European compendium of good practices on SHAFE](#) and on SiDLY's [website](#).

Did you know?

In Ireland the average cost of falls is €13,809 per person. With a fall detection device and 99 % of effectiveness with using it the incremental benefit is €11,390 in year one.

Source: <https://hih.ie/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/4316-CareClip-Economic-Impact-Final-Report.pdf>

What should be taken into consideration before the purchase?

There are several things to be considered before the purchase of a device: the type of system, if it is automatic, if fall detection system is in the package, what is the cost of the device and additional fees, if the design is suitable for the user.

Medical alert systems and fall detection systems are not the same. Not all fall detection systems are automatic. In some systems, the user has to make a call to family, caregiver or to the doctor. Moreover, not all medical alert systems come with fall detection sensors. Sometimes they are part of a package but sometimes they are supplementary with an additional fee. The cost of the device and additional fees such as subscription may vary between different companies.

Before choosing a specific system, research and compare medical alert device providers and products. While the fall detection technology is similar between companies, the service may offer different benefits. A call to the alert company or a visit to their website may help to understand what fall detection technology is currently offered. It could be useful in determining which device is suitable for a particular person.

If you want to know more go to SMART.

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 BUILT | **MODULE 6** | **CHAPTER 4**

All automatic detection medical alert systems allow the user to summon help without having to press the call button.

- True
- False

Chapter summary

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

1

You have learned about fall detection devices.

2

This knowledge will help you to choose fall detection device for older adult.

3

You may help other facilitators to choose fall detection device for older adult.

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

1

You know different types of fall detection devices

2

You can give examples of fall detection technologies

3

You know what should be considered before the purchase of fall detection devices

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

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Quiz

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 BUILT **MODULE 6**

Match fall risk factors with the proper groups of factors.

Behavioural risk factors	Diabetes
Environmental risk factors	Difficult financial situation
Biological factors	Smoking and sedentary lifestyle
Socioeconomic risk factors	Insufficient lightning

Module summary

1

You have learned about: the techniques for safe movement of older adults, the main causes and consequences of falls in old age, inexpensive and simple strategies to reduce the risk of fall at home and fall detection devices.

2

This knowledge will help you to understand the importance of prevention and risk reduction in terms of falls in old age.

3

You may help other facilitators to reduce risk of falls in older adults' apartments.

4

You have acquired skills of presenting safe movement techniques for older adults, removing mobility risks in older adults' apartments and helping with purchase of fall detection devices.

5

This course will influence your perception of older adults' safe movement at home and the reduction of different risk factors in terms of mobility at home.

Module completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this module!

Summary of acquired skills

1

You know the importance of mobility and the main factors and consequences of falls

2

You know strategies that are helpful for older adults to reduce risk of falls at home

3

You can give examples of fall detection devices and help in choosing one

What is next?

Now you can repeat the module, follow our study recommendation or go to the next one by clicking on one of the buttons below.

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